

Scalable Data-Rate Near-Lossless Hyperspectral Image Compression Based on Parallel Implementation of CCSDS-123.0-B-2

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1 INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral imaging is recognized as a cornerstone remote sensing technology. The explosive growth in hyperspectral image data volume (several TBs per orbit) and instrument data rates (in the range of 20 Gbps), compete with limited available on-board storage resources and downlink bandwidth, making hyperspectral image data compression a mission critical on-board data processing task. Near-lossless compression, is a quality controlled method where the absolute and/or relative maximum error between each pixel of the original and reconstructed image is bounded by some user-defined value, usually less than the sensor noise. In this context, the Multispectral Hyperspectral Data Compression (SLS-MHDC) Working Group of the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) recently released the new Issue 2 "Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression" standard CCSDS-123.0-B-2 [1]. This new issue improves on its CCSDS-123.0-B-1 lossless predecessor [2], by providing near lossless compression capability with user-defined absolute and/or relative error limits using an internal, closed-loop quantizer, as well as, by introducing a Hybrid Entropy Coder option capable of reaching sub 1 bit-per-pixel compression. The internal closed-loop quantizer of near-lossless prediction option introduced in CCSDS-123.0-B-2 introduces data dependencies, being the data-rate performance bottleneck for the near-lossless option. On the other hand, Hybrid Entropy Coder is an already-proven design, being capable to provide 1 sample-per-cycle and achieves throughput at 305 MSamples/s (4.88 Gbps) as introduced for the first time in [3].

Apart from the compression needs, on-board applications require devices that are capable of high-performance with low power consumption and radiation hardness characteristics. The current state-of-the-art SRAM-based FPGA technology offers Radiation Hardening By-Design (RHBD), high density and dynamic partial reconfiguration for in-flight adaptability and Time-Space Partitioning (TSP) of on-board data processing tasks. An excellent example of such technology is the RHBD Xilinx Kintex-Ultrascale XQRKU060 FPGA which provides exceptional hardness to Single-Event-Upset (SEU), typical immunity of 80MeV-cm²/mg to Single-Event Latchup (SEL), data path protection from Single-Event Transients (SET) and maximum tolerance of 100 Krad to Total Ionizing Dose (TID). The XQRKU060 FPGA offers those technological advantages and is considered a suitable device for on-board payload data processing applications due to its ability to support upgrades after launch, greatly enhancing mission profile and extending valuable mission life time.

In this paper, to provide data-rate performance in the range of several Gbps as required by several next-generation space missions, we introduce a scalable, parallel architecture and implementation for CCSDS 123.0-B-2 based compression leveraging segmentation along the x-axis of the spectral cube which enables scalable data-rate performance, provides identical compression performance with y-axis segmentation used in previous works but contrary to y-axis segmentation, it enables a constant embedded memory footprint for storing the small three-dimensional neighborhood required for prediction operation, regardless of the number of segments. The proposed architecture for the Hyperspectral Compression Engine (HCE) bypasses the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 internal quantizer data-rate performance bottleneck by employing, external, hardware-friendly quantization, operating the Predictor in lossless mode and leveraging Hybrid Entropy Coder superiority for low-entropy data, present either when near-lossless compression is applied or when lossless compression is used for low-entropy images.

The introduced scalable, parallel architecture is described in portable VHDL RTL and it is implemented, validated and demonstrated in-house on a commercially available Xilinx KCU105 development board hosting a Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale XCKU040 SRAM FPGA using state-of-the-art SpaceFibre serial link interface IP Cores and test equipment. Moreover, it has also been validated and demonstrated on a AIRBUS D&S breadboard hosting an XCKU060 device, as the compression

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 compressor [1]

element of the Hi-SIDE H2020 High-Speed Data-Chain project. Thus, the proposed architecture is directly transferable to the Xilinx Radiation-Tolerant Kintex UltraScale XQRKU060 space-grade devices for space deployments.

A single HCE achieves a constant throughput performance of 285 MSamples/s (4.56 Gbps), while the use of five parallel compression engines, according to the introduced architecture, can achieve 13.75 GSamples/s (22 Gbps). Scalability is only limited by the available FPGA resources and the high-speed serial interface technology. To the best of our knowledge, this is the highest, scalable data-rate performance of near-lossless compression functionality based on CCSDS-123.0-B-2 algorithm implemented in FPGA technology, targeting a space-grade platform for future ESA missions and next-generation payloads.

The rest of this contribution is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background information about the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Recommended Standard, while Section 3 describes the introduced architecture and its parallelization. Section 4 provides experimental results including the validation and demonstration of the proposed design on Xilinx KCU105 development board interfacing with SpaceFibre, as well as resource and throughput performance statistics of the implemented design. Section 5 presents related work and comparisons. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 BACKGROUND

The CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard was designed to provide an effective method of performing lossless and near-lossless compression of three-dimensional image data with low implementation complexity for space-borne imagers. Near-lossless compression refers to the ability to perform compression such that the maximum error in the reconstructed image can be limited to a user-specified bound by adjusting the absolute and/or relative error parameters during quantization. Fig.1 shows a block diagram schematic of the compression standard.

Incoming image samples, denoted as $s_z(t)$ where $t = y \cdot N_x + x$, $x = 0, \dots, N_x - 1$, $y = 0, \dots, N_y - 1$, $z = 0, \dots, N_z - 1$ are the spacial and spectral coordinates (N_x columns, N_y rows, N_z bands), enter at compressor's input. Image samples produced by multispectral and hyperspectral imagers are typically interleaved in one of three common orderings: z,y,x (Band SeQuential [BSQ]), y,x,z (Band Interleaved-by-Pixel [BIP]) and y,z,x (Band Interleaved-by-Line [BIL]). In BSQ the compression of all image samples of a spectral band is computed before processing the following bands; in BIP a sample is compressed for all the spectral bands before processing next samples; finally, in BIL each line of samples is compressed for all the bands before processing the next lines.

The Predictor uses a low-complexity adaptive linear prediction method to predict the value of each sample based on the values of nearby samples in a small three-dimensional neighborhood. Prediction can be performed causally in a single pass through the image, making use of an adaptively weighted prediction algorithm. Since the original input samples will not be available to the decompressor due to lossy compression, the predictor performs calculations based on sample representatives $s''_z(t)$ instead.

Besides using sample representatives, the Predictor in Issue 2 also differs from Issue 1 in that each prediction residual $\Delta_z(t)$, that is, the difference between the predicted and actual sample values, is quantized using a uniform quantizer. The quantizer step size is controlled via an absolute error limit (so that samples can be reconstructed with a user-specified error bound) and/or a relative error limit (so that samples predicted to have smaller magnitude can be reconstructed with lower error). Lossless compression in a band is obtained by setting both the absolute and relative error limits to zero. The inclusion of the quantization step inside the prediction loop, while enables better compression performance, implies the need for a local decoder to reconstruct pixel values in the prediction neighborhood, introducing data dependencies under BIP ordering which hinders deep pipelining and therefore high-throughput. The quantized prediction residual $q_z(t)$ is then mapped to an unsigned integer mapped quantizer index $\delta_z(t)$, making up the output of the Predictor.

The Encoder receives the Predictor's mapped quantizer indices, $\delta_z(t)$, and encodes them using a family of codes. The Standard describes three possible Encoder options, the Sample Adaptive and the Block-Adaptive from the previous Issue 1, as well as, the new Hybrid Entropy Coder. The CCSDS-120.2-G-2 Informational Report [4] includes detailed benchmarks of the encoders and highlights that even though the Hybrid Entropy Coder is the more complex encoder option, it is designed to provide enhanced compression performance for low-entropy data, when near-lossless compression

Fig. 2: CCSDS-123.0 Lossless Predictor and Hybrid Entropy Coder top-level block diagrams

is used. Moreover, even if lossless compression is used, improved compression performance can be provided compared to other encoders. A comprehensive review of the Issue 2 Standard can also be found at [5].

3 DESIGN ARCHITECTURE

3.1 Hyperspectral Compression Engine based on CCSDS-123.0-B-2 with External Quantization

The proposed architecture of a single Hyperspectral Compression Engine (HCE) IP Core based on CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard is based around an external quantization scheme with Predictor and Hybrid Entropy Coder. The quantization step performance bottleneck is removed from the prediction loop and an external hardware-friendly uniform quantizer is introduced with quantization step defined as a power-of-2. The proposed external quantizer can be described as $I_Q = I/2^\Delta$, where I and I_Q are the original and quantized images respectively, and can be implemented by cutting off the Δ least significant bits of the incoming image samples. The HCE features a per-band quantization option besides a global quantization step for all bands, allowing users to adjust the quantization step of any band in order to boost the compression performance. A small internal memory is used to store the quantization steps - more specifically the number cutoff bits - for all bands during configuration of the HCE.

Using an external quantizer, the Predictor now operates in lossless mode, exempt of any additional data dependency across z-axis in BIP order, which enables deep-pipelining and high-throughput performance exploiting inherent task-level parallelism (multi-threading by switching among bands). This idea was introduced for the first time in the open literature in [6] and further exploited in previous [7] [8] and other related work [9]. The implementation of the lossless Predictor as in [7] [8] (Fig. 2a), features the full prediction mode using neighbour-oriented sums for $P = 3$ prediction bands. It mainly consists of the *Spectral Slice Buffer* and the *Predictor* units. *Spectral Slice Buffer* is a cascading FIFO scheme used for providing the *Predictor* unit with the neighboring pixels required to begin with the prediction procedure. The *Predictor* unit comprises of several pipelined sub-units that calculate the prediction estimate and map its difference with the current image sample to an unsigned integer.

A state-of-the-art Hybrid Entropy Coder architecture is used, introduced for the first time in [3], also operating in BIP order and capable of providing sample-per-cycle throughput and thus high data-rate performance. Its architecture consists of several pipelined sub-units (Fig. 2b), where the incoming mapped predicted residuals ($\delta_z(t)$) from the Predictor's output are encoded by a high entropy or a low entropy codeword based on code selection statistics stored in the form of a counter ($\Gamma(t)$) and a high-resolution accumulator ($\tilde{\Sigma}_z(t)$). High entropy codes are selected from Golomb families of codes, whereas low entropy codes are selected out of 16 variable-to-variable length codes that are able to encode multiple symbols to a single codeword. Low entropy code selection forms a feedback loop related to the codetable selection that contains the design's critical path. Lastly, the codewords from the encoder are packed to 64-bit packets, by a Variable-Length Code (VLC) packer and emitted to the output.

The IP Core interfaces are employing AXI4-Stream based I/O, supporting flow control using the protocol *ready/valid* handshake. It is deeply pipelined exploiting a systolic latency insensitive design pattern, with elastic buffers [10] as pipeline registers. The elastic buffers use AXI4-Stream handshaking and allow for sample-per-cycle throughput when neither

Fig. 3: Compression data rate for *aviris_yellowstone_sc00* with external and in-loop quantization

source or sink are stalling. This design pattern avoids additional controllers for flow control, or superfluous buffering to manage sink side stalls. Configuration, status and control of the IP Core is performed with registers containing user-selected parameters for the Predictor/Encoder pair, as well as, the fidelity control parameters and execution commands.

3.2 Parallel Design

3.2.1 Image Segmentation

The proposed scalable parallel architecture exploits CCSDS-123-B-2 segment-level parallelism by partitioning along the X-axis of the spectral cube and integrating multiple HCE IP Cores. Partitioning along the X-axis, for the first time to the open literature to the best of our knowledge, does not affect memory footprint, since spectral slice buffering required for the predictor to access the small three-dimensional neighborhood, is partitioned among the different parallel cores. We remark that compression performance for X-axis partitioning is nearly identical and for some images better when compared to Y-axis partitioning [4], while custom weight initialization does not improve performance for large segments. Moreover, segmentation inherently limits the effects of potential data corruption on the reconstructed image only to the affected image segment, thus leading to a more robust compression scheme.

In order to evaluate the compression performance of the external quantization method in comparison to the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 internal quantizer, we compared near-lossless compression with both options on the AVIRIS scene 0 hyper-spectral cube benchmark (*aviris_yellowstone_sc00*) segmented on the X-axis, using both the pre-quantization method with quantization step $Q = 2, 4, 8, 16$, and the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Absolute Error Limit parameter $A^* = 1, 2, 4, 8$, while the rest of parameters were the same for both compression options. The values of Q and A^* are selected in order to maintain the same Peak Absolute Error (PAE) between the original image and the decompressed image for both options. Each image segment is compressed independently, then by summing the compressed segment sizes we compute the total compression performance in terms of bits-per-sample. Fig. 4 validates the argument of Green Book [4] that the increase in data volume arising from partitioning an image into segments may be modest if image segments are not very small while pre-quantization provides competitive results. Finally, the rate-distortion graph of Fig. 3 proves that pre-quantization can be a favorable trade-off since it enable high-data rate performance at similar compression quality when compared to CCSDS-123.0-B-2 internal quantizer.

3.2.2 Hardware Implementation

The presented hardware implementation of the HCE IP Core based on CCSDS-123.0-B-2 is developed in portable VHDL RTL targeting Xilinx Kintex-Ultrascale XCKU040-2FFVA1156E SRAM FPGA, and thus is directly transferable to the Xilinx Radiation Tolerant XQRKU060 FPGA. The supported features are: i) dynamic range up to 16 bits-per-pixel-per-band (bpppb), ii) up to 4096 rows and columns and up to 512 bands, iii) BIP pixel order, iv) 3 prediction bands, v) full prediction mode, vi) neighbor-oriented local sums, vii) user-defined fidelity control per band and viii) the Hybrid Entropy Coder. The implementation is based around SpaceFibre (ECSSE-ST-50-11C) test equipment, provided by STAR-Dundee, to interface the Xilinx KCU105 development board, hosting the XCKU040 device, and match standard space deployment. SpaceFibre is a very high-speed (5 Gbit/s) serial link and network technology, designed specifically for use on board spacecraft. SpaceFibre interface is provided by a provided IP Core by STAR-Dundee, communicating with the compressor IP Core through standard 128-bit AXI4-Stream Interfaces for data transfers and an Advanced Peripheral Bus

Fig. 4: Rate-distortion for compression with external and in-loop quantization for 1 and 5 parallel cores

Fig. 5: Parallel design of compressor IP-core based on CCSDS-123.0-B-2

(APB) interface for configuration, status and control by accessing a provided Remote Memory Access Protocol (RMAP) memory space. Moreover, using SpaceFibre for direct configuration and control eliminates the need of an embedded CPU or external memory, simplifying the overall system design and integration.

The parallel architecture (Fig. 5) currently supports 5 HCE IP cores, with the upper bound determined by the available device resources and spectral cube dimensions. Data segmentation and distribution to the cores is handled by a dedicated hardware (*Dispatcher*), implementing a round-robin scheduling scheme supplying each HCE IP core with an equal image segment from the incoming data stream.

A standard PC emulating Electronic Ground Support Equipment (EGSE) hosting the SpaceFibre equipment is provided to connect the KCU105 board and exchange data using the STAR-System API and graphical applications. Data transmission is performed with a single SpaceFibre Link Virtual Channel (VC), while compressed data of each core are transmitted back to the EGSE PC using an individual Virtual Channel per core. This excludes re-arranging the compressed image segments to form a single compressed image, as each compressed image segment is considered a self-contained downlink packet that can be scheduled for transmission, contributing to the overall system robustness.

The compressor is configured by user-defined run-time configurable parameters and compile-time VHDL generics. Run-time parameters address to CCSDS-123.0-B-2 parameters regarding the image dynamic range (D), the image dimensions (N_x, N_y, N_z), Predictor's Weight Update Scaling Exponent Change Interval (t_{inc}), Weight Update Scaling Exponent Parameters (ν_{min}, ν_{max}) and Hybrid Entropy Coder's Unary Length Limit (U_{max}), Initial Count Exponent (γ_0) and Rescaling Counter Size (γ^*). In addition, extra parameters are added for the quantization step per-band regarding the shift amount of the power-of-two quantizer. The IP core supports up to 512 bands with parameters q_shift_0 to q_shift_511 determining the quantization shift amount for each band. In case the shifting for all bands is the same, the q_shift_flag can be raised and q_shift value will be used for all bands, bypassing the rest of quantization parameters. Compile-time generics are also used to bound the image dimensions ($g_Nx_max, g_Ny_max, g_Nz_max, g_Nz_min$) and the number of cores (g_cores_num). Conditional VHDL structures at compile time instantiate the number of HCE Cores instructed by g_cores_num along with the number and depth of the buffer queues and the Dispatcher's counter limits.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Design Implementation

Implementation on the target device was performed using a configuration for the AVIRIS ($680 \times 512 \times 224$, 16bpppb) hyperspectral instruments, which are typical hyperspectral sensors for space application and commonly used in literature, using Xilinx Vivado 2020.2 for synthesis and place and route (PnR), optimizing for performance.

Implementation results for one up to five parallel HCE cores are shown in Table 1. The design uses two clocks, one system clock at maximum achievable frequency shared among the HCE cores, AXI4-Stream and APB peripherals and a 156.25 MHz clock required by the SpaceFibre IP Core handling clock-domain-crossing for the AXI4-Stream and APB interfaces internally. A single core configuration achieves 285 MHz of maximal operational frequency and data rate of 285 Msamples/s (4.56 Gbps), while a five core configuration is clocked at 275 MHz with a potential data-rate of 1375 MSamples/s (22 Gbps) (assuming a five-lane SpaceFibre link is available).

4.2 Design Verification and Validation

The IP core is verified using FPGA-in-the-loop based verification directly on target device hosted on commercial Xilinx KCU105 development board, comparing results against golden data produced by the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 official golden model binaries provided by Centre National d'Études Spatiales (CNES). The verification/validation and demonstration

Tab. 1: Implementation statistics on the XCKU040 for CCSDS-123.0-B-2 parallel design for AVIRIS images

Instrument	AVIRIS 680x512x224, 16bpppb					
	1 core	2 cores	3 cores	4 cores	5 cores	
Device Resources	LUT	18861 (7.78%)	32033 (13.21%)	44241 (18.25%)	56318 (23.23%)	67362 (27.79%)
	FF	21395 (4.41%)	34597 (7.14%)	47252 (9.75%)	58294 (11.02%)	68987 (14.23%)
	DSP	23 (1.2%)	46 (2.40%)	69 (3.56%)	92 (4.8%)	115 (6%)
	BRAM	104 (17.33%)	276 (46.00%)	295 (49.08%)	296 (49.33%)	306 (51%)
Frequency	285 MHz	280 MHz	275 MHz	270 MHz	275 MHz	
Power Est. ⁽¹⁾	1.091 W	3.655 W	3.661 W	3.899 W	4.222 W	
MSamples/s	285	560	825	1080	1375	
Gbps @16bpppb	4.56	8.96	13.2	17.28	22	

⁽¹⁾reported for the HCE IP core, excluding consumption of SpaceFibre IP core and GTH transceivers of the KC105 device.

set-up is built around the provided SpaceFibre test equipment interfacing the Xilinx KCU105 board matching standard space deployment. The set-up includes the EGSE PC hosting STAR-Ultra PCIe board connected to the KCU105 board using a QSFP to SFP+ cable assembly. SpaceFibre interface VHDL IP Cores are also instantiated in the FPGA design to provide AXI4-Stream interface with the Compressor IP Core data inputs and compressed output over a single or multiple data Virtual Channel (VC) according to the number of cores used. A single-lane SpaceFibre link is able to provide 6.25 Gbps (effective 5.0 Gbps) data-rate, while the addition of extra lanes (up to 4 lanes) multiplies the data-rate accordingly. KCU105 development board supports up to two SpaceFibre lanes, which proved sufficient for demonstrating our architecture for one and two parallel cores.

Verification/validation used the AVIRIS hawaii (614x512x224 @14bpppb), maine (680x512x224 @14bpppb) and yellowstone scene 0 (680x512x224 @16bpppb) hyperspectral images, whose dimensions are typical for space data systems. Test suites with exhaustive testings of all predictor/encoder parameters were automatically run, allowed by custom Python scripts and STAR-API applications. Moreover, the design with 2 parallel cores has also been validated on an AIRBUS D&S breadboard hosting an XCKU060 device and was demonstrated as the compressor element of the High-Speed Data Chain (HSDC) system demonstration in the framework of H2020 Hi-SIDE project (<https://www.hi-side.space/hi-side>). Thus, the proposed architecture is directly transferable to the Xilinx Radiation-Tolerant XQRKU060 space-grade devices for space deployment.

4.3 Comparison with Previous Works

To date, there are few known FPGA implementations of CCSDS-123.0-B-2 in literature. Table 2 summarizes all known and related implementations of CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard in comparison to our work. Barrios et al. in [11] presented the first implementation of the standard developed with High-Level Synthesis (HLS) methods targeting a Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale XCKU040 FPGA device. The developed IP core follows the BIL pixel order featuring both the near-lossless Predictor and the Hybrid Entropy Coder achieving data-rate of 17.86 MSamples/s.

Another HLS implementation of near-lossless compressor based CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard, targeting a Xilinx Zynq Ultrascale+ ZU19EG MPSoC device is presented in [12]. This work, similarly to our approach, adds a pre-quantization stage prior to the predictor loop leading to a more hardware-friendly version of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard. Furthermore, a simple data encryption scheme is also added to the compressed data by randomly flipping the sign of the predictor residuals. The implemented FPGA design was tested with a variety of multispectral images as well as Synthetic-Aperture Radar (SAR) data, achieving data-rate of 10 MSamples/s in median.

Recently, a high-performance VHDL implementation of CCSDS-123.0-B-2 in Bascos et. al [13] achieved 4.0 Gbps @ 250MHz targeting XQRKU060 FPGA by introducing an extensive pixel reordering scheme in order to read BIP image data diagonally eliminating data dependencies across the Z-axis during the prediction stage. To do so, it requires to buffer N_z^2 samples, which significantly impacts BRAM resources. This limits the applicability of segment-level parallelism that can be exploited to achieve very-high data-rate, on-board payload hyperspectral image compression on hundreds of spectral bands, as required for several next generation space missions. Furthermore, the pixel reordering scheme introduces a high latency (requires N_z^2 cycles) preventing its viability for real-time (on-the-fly) compression.

Finally, implementations of the Fast Lossless Extended (FLEX) algorithm [16] [17] [18], which is the algorithmic predecessor for CCSDS-123.0-B-2 (with the Hybrid Entropy Coder being an extension of the FLEX's original Hybrid Entropy Coder), can be considered for comparison purposes. The NASA JPL implementation by Keymeulen et al. [19] [14] as a part of a complete avionics system for data acquisition, cloud screening, and data compression implements compression with FLEX. Due to the complexity and data dependencies in near-lossless mode, FLEX does not achieve a high performance in a single core, as opposed to other lossless-only compressors. Regardless, the authors implement segmentation across the Y-axis to increase throughput performance and present a variant of FLEX in an airborne demonstration using COTS parts. On an Alpha Data board with a Virtex-7 VX690T-3 FPGA, FLEX achieves 106 MSamples/s using 15 parallel cores and 32-line high segments. A software component on a COTS PC performs real-time data analysis and schedules data movements between sensor, FPGA and CPU over PCIe.

Tab. 2: Comparison of CCSDS-123.0-B-2 FPGA Accelerators

	Keymeulen et al. [14]		Barrios et al. [15]	Ros et al. [12]	Báscones et al. [13]		This work
Impl. Method	VHDL		HLS	HLS	VHDL		VHDL
Image size (N_x, N_y, N_z)	640,480,480		677,512,224	32768,16384,8	680,512,224		680,512,224
Pixel Order	BIP		BIL	BIL	BIP ⁽¹⁾		BIP
Target Device	Virtex-7 VX960T		Kintex Ultrascale XCKU040	Zynq Ultrascale+ ZU19EG	Kintex Ultrascale XQRKU060		Kintex Ultrascale XCKU040
Speed Grade	3		1	n/a	1		2
Parallelism	1	16	1	1	1		5
LUTs	73514	297807	17185	196087	16458		18861 67362
FFs	82056	260750	11915	149406	15707		21395 68987
BRAMs	60	556	85	268	188		104 306
Power (W)	7.84	11.40	2.48	n/a	1.21		1.09 4.222
Throughput (MSamples/s)	3.4	106	17.86	10 ⁽²⁾	284.5		285 1375

¹ Uses internal re-ordering to Frame Internal Interleaved-by-Diagonal (FID)
² In median among all test data

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents an IP Core based on CCSDS-123.0-B-2 compression standard described in portable VHDL RTL targeting Xilinx KCU040 SRAM FPGA and thus directly transferable to XQRKU060 space-grade devices for space deployment. With the removal of the in-loop prediction quantizer externally, the IP Core maintains both lossless and near-lossless compression options by controlling the quantization step achieving single core data rate performance of 285 MSamples/s (4.46 Gbps). Furthermore, a parallel implementation exploiting the image segmentation on X-axis further improves performance, by achieving data rate of 1375 MSamples/s (22 Gbps) with five parallel cores. The introduced architecture is validated and demonstrated on a commercially available Xilinx KCU105 development board hosting a Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale XCKU040 SRAM FPGA using state-of-the-art SpaceFibre (ECSS-E-ST-50-11C) interface and test equipment for validation to match space deployment. To the best of authors' knowledge this is the first parallel implementation of CCSDS-123-B-2 standard.

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